

RTV infection. Such symptoms were most common.

The disease is transmitted by brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens*. The incubation period of the causal agent in the insect was 5-21 days, usually 6-8 days. Five to 30% of the insects were active transmitters. The disease was not transmitted by sap, seeds, or soil or by 368 green leafhoppers *Nephotettix virescens* used to inoculate about 3,000 seedlings.

Disease symptoms were observed 7-14 days after inoculation of 7-day-old Taichung Native 1 (TN1) seedlings. Infected plants were yellow or pale yellow, even when fertilized adequately. TN1 plants infected at 2 months had RTV-like symptoms similar to those of naturally infected plants.

Although the unknown disease is similar to GSV, the two diseases differ:

1) the RTV-like symptom has never been described for GSV; 2) the disease is often lethal, particularly when plants are infected at early growth stages; and 3) *Oryza nivara*, the source of the resistance gene against GSV, is susceptible to the unknown disease (Table 1). Consequently, IR varieties with *O. nivara* genes for resistance to GSV are also susceptible (Table 2). These differences indicate the unknown disease may be a new virus disease or a strain of GSV. □

Table 1. Reaction of *Oryza nivara* to grassy stunt (GSV) and to the unknown disease, IRRI.

Trial	GSV			Unknown disease		
	Plants (no.)		Infection (%)	Plants (no.)		Infection (70)
	Inoculated	Infected		Inoculated	Infected	
I ^a	10	0	0	14	14	100
II ^a	11	0	0	11	9	82
III ^b	84	2	2.4	31	29	93.5

^a Inoculated at 3 weeks old using 15-20 insects/seedling. ^b Inoculated using the mass screening method for GSV.

Table 2. Reaction of IR varieties to grassy stunt (GSV) and to the unknown disease, IRRI.

Variety	GSV ^a			Unknown disease ^b		
	Plants (no.)		Infection (%)	Plants (no.)		Infection (%)
	Inoculated	Infected		Inoculated	Infected	
IR28	380	127	33.4	83	72	86.8
IR29	183	48	26.2	73	66	90.4
IR30	309	81	26.2	77	64	83.1
IR32	548	156	28.5	87	78	89.7
IR34	489	101	20.7	65	59	90.8
IR36	4467	1546	34.6	97	87	89.7
IR38	367	73	19.9	75	65	86.7
IR40	308	57	18.5	58	49	84.5
IR42	4225	1363	32.3	191	183	95.8
IR43	203	37	18.2	64	53	82.8
IR44	388	72	18.6	94	81	86.2
IR45	175	16	9.1	85	82	96.5
IR46	587	114	19.4	87	78	89.7
IR48	342	35	10.2	77	67	87.0
IR50	560	91	16.3	92	81	88.0
IR52	264	27	10.2	75	69	92.0
IR54	41	3	7.3	72	69	95.8

^a Combined data for GSV screening for 1980 and 1981. ^b Total of 2 trials (2 replications/trial).

Pest management and control INSECTS

Leaffolder outbreak in tarai belt of Nepal

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The rice leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée has recently become a serious rice pest in Nepal. In 1977, it became epidemic in some tarai districts and in hilly areas. In 1978, leaffolder incidence was high at Janakpur, Bara, and Parsa, and in some hilly areas around Kathmandu Valley. In 1979-80, infestation was high in the first crop at the Parwanipur Station and in adjacent areas.

The insect first appears in May and stays until November. Its life cycle is generally completed within 25-30 days; cycles can be observed by the appearance of large moth populations at 1-month intervals. In a rice season, 4-5 generations are completed. A June 1980 field survey showed pest incidence in most of the tarai; "hot pockets" were Janakpur, Kankai, Bara, and Parsa. Leaffolder incidence was heavy at Hardinath Agricultural Farm and in surrounding areas in Janakpur where about two-thirds of the leaves in infested fields were folded. Most of the fields were totally white and papery because the chlorophyll of the rice plants was completely eaten off. In some fields about 90% of the leaves were

folded.

Attack at early tillering stage was serious and the extent of the yield reduction it caused should be studied.

Brown planthopper resurgence on IR36 in Mindanao, Philippines

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During a baseline field trial for insect control recommendations in Sultan Kudarat Province, up to 5% brown planthopper (BPH) hopperburned hills